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Secondary Education And Values Re-Orientation In Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on secondary education and values re-orientation in secondary schools in Rivers State. The need to identify the values that are needed in secondary education, for effective school management that could enhance students self-employment and employers of labor in future. There are two (2) research questions and also two null hypotheses postulated for this study. The research design of the study was descriptive survey. 117,560 teachers and students served as the population of the study. The sample size of the study was 399 respondents obtained using Taro Yamane Formula and stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire with the title: Secondary Education and Values Re-Orientation in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (SEVROSSQ). The instrument was self-validated and a reliability index of 0.87 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha reliability method. Research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, there are types of curriculum reform with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State; and the respondents agreed to a high extent that, change and innovation are applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State. Hence, it was concluded that secondary education needs re-orientation in adding more values to education. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that government should ensure that every secondary school leaver acquire a skill before graduating from the school. Also, there should be training and retraining of teachers to enable them acquire skills that can be transferred to students, as this will encourage self-employment.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Values and Re-orientation

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education is very crucial in Educational upbringing of students. Secondary Education is particularly concerned with the values orientation, to strengthen language development of students and also preparing them for tertiary Education. This type of education includes the junior and senior secondary, Technical and Vocational Education. Apart from the foregoing levels of studies, there are other Educational programs, which include the mass literacy, Adult and non- formal Education and the Nomadic Education. From the foregoing, secondary Education system in the present is the junior and secondary schools. Buttressing this, National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) remarked that post-Basic Education is the Education children receive after a successful completion of nine (9) years of Basic

Education and passing the Basic Education certificate Examination (BECE). The secondary Education includes senior secondary education, higher school and continuing Education given in vocational Enterprise institution to enter Basic Education graduates that are not proceeding to senior secondary schools or to the tertiary level of Education.

The secondary Education (post-Basic Education, PBE) is to develop holders of the Basic Education certificates with the opportunity for Education of a higher level. A critic look at the secondary Education curriculum, school leavers should be graduates with added values that should be in line with the new trends of demand of the curriculum taught effectively and a mastery of what is taught to the students (National Policy on Education, 27-39). To offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles, to provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional levels, in order to provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational jobs specific skills for self-reliance and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development (FRN, 2014). The secondary Education curriculum (SEC) has also been re-structured to include the following core subjects: English studies, Mathematics, and one Trade with Entrepreneurship Studies, Computer Studies/ ICT and civic Education. The aim is to strengthen skills acquisition, language development and value orientation.

The poor conception of policy and lack of curriculum reform by the Government is one of the problems in Rivers state. In particular, there is public outcry over the failures of policies and non-application of changes in the curriculum of Government in both Federal and State levels. This ugly situation is widely reported across the nations, the agencies in charge of curriculum reform are the Nigerian Educational Research and Development council, (NERDC) and State Ministry of Education (SOME), teachers, and other people that plan the curriculum and gives approval to what should be taught. Ajuonuma, Asodike and Anyaogu (2015), remarked that continuity of education projects and policies by the succeeding government and because government is a continuum and should be run in the interest of the masses rather than the politicians. There should be co-ordination among the three levels of government from the local state and the Federal governments in providing and execution of programs and curriculum education to avoid conflict, confusion and failures.

Moreover, the non-participation of Education managers in taking decisions concerning the school system and curriculum reform. A decision is the selection of alternative course of action from available alternatives in order to achieve the given objective. Its aim is to make things happen in order to achieve an objective. Buttressing this, Nwachukwu (2006) remarked that it is safe to say that all managers are involved in decision making. The decision maker knows his or her objectives and will ensure maximizing the outcome. The current multiple stakeholders processes of management for secondary education are communities based organization, parents Alumni and the society.

Recent development in the educational sector concerning the counseling services center as a testimony against education organizers, administrators, and stakeholders in Rivers state. The ugly behavior find among students both in character, discipline, and examination malpractice. The government at the Federal, states and local levels should step up their funding on education because the cutbacks in government spending over the years in hitting very hard on the education sector (Ajuonuma, et al., 2015). They remarked that the government should ensure greater inflow of money on guidance and counseling services in our secondary schools. Moreover, there seem to be a consensus amongst the parents, teachers and administrators that though anyone can be called upon to re-orient the students, not everyone can re-orient students due to differences in intrinsic and extrinsic traits of the individual and as well training acquired. These are the factors that have affected re-orientation over the years. Thus, it was on this premise that this study sought to examine secondary education and values re-orientation in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Secondary education in Rivers State Nigeria is facing a critical challenge in terms of value re-orientation. The current curriculum and teaching methods are not adequately equipping students with the necessary values, skills, and knowledge to navigate the complexities of the 21st century. The emphasis on academic achievement has led to a neglect of essential life skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and

emotional intelligence. Furthermore, the prevailing value system in secondary education prioritizes individualism, competition, and material success over collective well-being, social responsibility, and environmental sustainability. This has resulted in a mismatch between the values promoted in schools and the needs of the broader society. Consequently, many secondary school leavers are ill-prepared to address the social, economic, and environmental challenges facing their communities, and are instead perpetuating the status quo. There is an urgent need to re-orient the values and focus of secondary education to prioritize holistic development, social responsibility, and environmental sustainability. Therefore, this study examined secondary education and values re-orientation in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine secondary education and values re-orientation in secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives sought to:

1. identify the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. determine the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What are the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Conceptual Clarification

Secondary Education

Education in Nigeria is divided into three (3) stages, namely, primary education, secondary education and tertiary education. The secondary education is the median education. It is the education received by a child in between the primary education and tertiary education. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014), secondary education is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage. Secondary education is a crucial tier in the hierarchy of education in Nigeria. It is the midway between primary and tertiary schools. It is the form of education that students receive after their primary education and or before their tertiary education. It is intended for pupils between the ages of 11-17. Secondary education is the budding ground for future professionals as well as the foundation for the discovering and classification of the specific fields of professions.

Prior to the independence of Nigeria through to 1982, secondary education lasted only five years. After the duration of five years, those who obtained the required qualifications were allowed for the two years of Higher School Certificate which qualifies them for university education. Thus the system allowed for three years junior and two years senior. However, discovering the need to enhance this tier of education with science and technical subjects, the curriculum was broadened to have its duration extended to six years.

Furthermore, FRN (2014) stated that the broad goals of secondary education shall be to;

- Prepare students for useful living within the society
- Prepare students for higher education

These broad goals of secondary education were further split into specific terms or objectives by the FRN (2014) as cited in Aduwa (2021) as follow:

- i. Secondary education will provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of sex, social status, religious or ethnic background.
- ii. Secondary education will offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles.
- iii. It will provide and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world's cultural heritage.
- iv. Secondary education will provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades;
- v. Secondary education will inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence.
- vi. It will foster National unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity.
- vii. Secondary education will raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals and live as good citizens.
- viii. Secondary education will provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development.

The goals of secondary education stated above covered the three (3) domains of the learners, namely, cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. Secondary education is a stage of education that exposes the students to wide ranges of subject areas when compared to primary education and tertiary education (Aduwa, 2021). From 1960 till date, several reforms have been carried out by the federal government of Nigerian on secondary education. The essence of all these reforms is to ensure that there is high standard of secondary education in Nigeria. One of these reforms is the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme. The launch of universal basic education (UBE) in 1999 as a follow up to the 1977 universal free primary education (UPE) was also an important educational milestone which became a major focus of government in line with its drive to reform the sector.

Despite all the reforms carried out by the federal government of Nigeria over the years on secondary education, secondary education in Nigeria still suffer a lot of setbacks. The standard of students in secondary schools still remained low day by day (Aduwa, 2021). Although, there are secondary schools owned by the state governments, federal government and private individuals. Each provides the human and material resources needed by their schools. The percentage of secondary schools owned by the state governments is relatively higher than the percentages of secondary schools owned by the federal government and the private individuals. But, the majority of the secondary schools controlled and managed by the various state governments, especially those schools located in the rural areas, does not really look like ideal school environments.

Re-Orientation and Value

Accordingly vocabulary.com (2020) in Uche, Oluwuo and Abraham (2020) remarked three set of meaning to re-orientation. It is the action of changing the focus or direction of something. It is the act of changing direction in a way of rethinking, and way of approaching something. It may be an ideas, projects, events, time and policies and programs. Dictionary of Geography (2015) opined value as the importance, worth, or usefulness of something. However, everything important is worthwhile which is inculcated to students through education in either formal or informal settings. It is a re-assessment on the curriculum of course, because it has gone off-course or off-line, and value expected from it is lost. The need to redeem education arises through value re-orientation (Okoroafor, 2012). Re-orientation is bringing back the lost glory or values in secondary school system. The absence of these values is what went wrong with the system. Questions like, is there any value added to school leavers after secondary education? How can one continue after secondary education to the tertiary Education?

Educational Re-Orientation

When deliberate efforts have been made to cause some changes in Education, it reflected on the students, as a change. Educational re-orientation is bringing back the lost glory in education. It is improving the existing status quo to match with the changes and innovations in the society. Yesterday’s educational technologies cannot be used for today school and still expect the system to meet with global demands on education. We must add new things and improve upon the old ones to meet the demands of the changing society with fast technological drives. Thus, changes in curriculum, new methods and skills that gears towards improving teaching and learning (Ajuonuma, et al., 2015). These changes are reflected on teacher’s professional skill and students’ direction of change. The change redirects and introduces new values in Education. Education as viewed by Afangideh and Aliezi as cited in Uche, et al (2020) as the transmission of cultural knowledge, skills and values of people to its younger ones, needy and desiring folks from generations to generations.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Rivers state with the teachers population of five thousand, eight hundred and thirty three (5,833) and estimated students population of one hundred eleven thousand, five hundred and sixty (111,560), totaling 117,393. A sample size of 399 was drawn from the entire population using Taro Yamane formula, while the sampling technique adopted was a stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled: Secondary Education and Values Re-Oriented in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (SEVROSSQ). The instrument was self-validated and a reliability index of 0.87 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha reliability method. A total of 399 copies of the questionnaire were administered and 376 copies were retrieved, resulting in 94% retrieval rate. Research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Teachers and Students on the Type of Curriculum Reform that Agrees with Value Re-Oriented Delivered by the Teachers and Received by Students of Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	Good knowledge and skillful art of the subject matters.	3.51	0.61	Agreed
2.	Improved self-reliance skill in value re-orientation.	3.20	0.59	Agreed
3.	Helping students develop new knowledge directed toward value reorientation.	3.32	0.79	Agreed
4.	Promoting critical thinking in students.	3.16	0.69	Agreed
5.	Making the lesson students centered and making education to be sustainable.	3.41	0.51	Agreed
6.	Assessment of students regularly.	3.32	0.52	Agreed
7.	Giving room for questions and answers.	2.93	0.62	Agreed
8.	Effectiveness in curriculum reform instructional strategies affects value re-orientation.	2.42	0.44	Disagreed
9.	Promoting educational sustainability.	3.44	0.81	Agreed
10	Helping students to develop value reorientation education.	3.35	0.71	Agreed
11	Improving confidence, good moral standards towards value reorientation.	2.80	0.61	Agreed
	Grand mean	3.16	0.61	Agreed

Data on Table 1 revealed that the respondents agreed on the questionnaire items on teachers and students value re-orientation for education in secondary schools. It was deduced from items 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,9,10 and 11 which had mean scores above 2.50. Mean cut off mark earlier set as agreed, with the exception of item 8 which disagreed that effective curriculum content instructional strategies required for value re-orientation in secondary education level.

However, the grand mean of 3.16 with standard deviation value of 0.61, which indicates that the respondents were homogenous in their response towards value re-orientation in secondary education.

Research Question Two: *What are the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Teachers and Students on the Levels of Change and Innovation Applied by the Teachers and Received by the Students of Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
12.	Teaches students to inculcate the changes and innovations.	3.18	0.65	High Extent
13.	Exposes students to diver views and opinion on new ideas.	3.36	0.55	High Extent
14.	Equip students with the useful knowledge.	3.29	0.71	High Extent
15.	Teaches students the value of pride and fraud.	2.22	0.42	Low Extent
16.	Making it easy to detect student problems.	3.41	0.59	High Extent
17.	Foster co-operation amongst students.	3.32	0.57	High Extent
18.	Inspires students for healthy academic competition.	2.96	0.67	High Extent
19.	Helps students develop new ideas and knowledge.	2.98	0.72	High Extent
20.	Teaches self- employed learning.	2.36	0.44	Low Extent
21.	Helps in employment of labor.	3.35	0.65	High Extent
	Grand Mean	3.10	0.67	High Extent

Data on table 2, revealed that the respondents agreed on a high extent on the questionnaire items that the level of achievement of value re-orientation required for change and innovation by teachers and students. This can be deduced from items 12,13,14,16,17,18,19 and 21,which had mean scores above 2.50 with exceptions of items 15 and 20 which had mean scores above 2.50 as calculated value and exception of items of 15 and 20 which disagreed to a low extent that value re-orientation teaches the value of pride and fraud and self-employed learning.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses One: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test Analysis on the Significant Difference between the Mean Scores of Teachers and Students on the Type of Curriculum Reform that Agrees with Value Re-Orientation Delivered by the Teachers and Received by Students of Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Group	Mean	SD	N	df	z-calculated	z-critical	Decision
Teachers	3.16	0.61	111	374	0.70	1.96	Ho ₁ Accepted
Students	3.09	0.63	265				

Data in table 3 revealed that the calculated value of 0.70 was less than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance, and 374 degree of freedom. This implies that, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the type of curriculum reform delivered by teachers and that received by students in secondary schools was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and students on the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test Analysis on the Significant Difference between the Mean Scores of Teachers and Students on the Levels of Change and Innovation Applied by the Teachers and Received by the Students of Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Group	Mean	SD	N	df	z-calculated	z-critical	Decision
Teachers	3.16	0.61	111	374	0.50	1.96	Ho ₂ Accepted
Students	3.09	0.63	265				

Data in table 4 revealed that the calculated value of 0.50 was less than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance and 374 degree of freedom. This implies that, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of data analyses presented on Table 1 indicated that the respondents agreed that all the items except item 8, are the type of curriculum reform with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State. This highlights the fact that the right curriculum content enhance teachers' effectiveness and student's performance in schools. This finding is in line with Ogah, et al (2009), Alyssa (2018), Aduwa (2020) and UNESCO (2020) who in their studies found that, curriculum reform is changing or improving the already existing curriculum to the societal needs and educational objectives and the changing in the society. The teacher is expected to have knowledge of the curriculum that will enhance teaching and learning effective. They are the major implementer of the curriculum and the values needed by the society. The values are discipline, resilience, accountability and productivity. No wonder the hypothesis tested showed that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and students on the type of curriculum reform that agrees with value re-orientation delivered by the teachers and received by students of secondary schools in Rivers State

The result of data analyses presented on Table 2 also revealed that respondents agreed to a high extent that, change and innovation are applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings agreed with Ajuonuma, et al (2015) and Aduwa (2021) who found that, educational innovation is the type of educational change that is positive and seeks improvement in the existing status quo. It scope may be narrow but are designed to correct some features of the educational system. This is because teachers major agent of change and innovation and must set up the pace for learning opportunities aimed at facilitating students with skills and the right knowledge needed for the

time. Thus, the hypothesis tested revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students on the levels of change and innovation applied by the teachers and received by the students of secondary schools in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

This study clearly observed that both professional teachers and students all needed change and innovation in facilitating learning. It is expected that effort be made to ensure that the right values are imbibe to students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following were recommended based on the findings:

1. Government should ensure that every young school leaver should acquire at least one trade or skill before graduating.
2. Regular training and re-training of teachers on issues of acquisition of skill to enable them transfer to students to encourage self-employment and employers of labor.

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